

THE HISTORY OF RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND SOUTH KOREA IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION IS AN OPPORTUNITY TO A NEW STAGE

Qalandar Rustamov Ravshan o'g'li
3rd stage student of Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizomi
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8142802>

Annotation: This article describes the establishment, development and prospects of cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea in the field of education. Also the decisions of the presidents and governments of the two countries, the relationship between universities are included.

Keywords: Education, development, cooperation, relation, partnership, information, economic, policy

After gaining political independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan joined the process of forming a new model of international relations as a full member of the world community. The Republic of Uzbekistan pursued an open foreign policy, and as a result, since the independence, international organizations and states in the world sought to establish broad cooperation with the Republic of Uzbekistan. Establishing cooperation with international organizations and other countries in the world was beneficial in every way. As a result, Uzbekistan has been cooperating with many countries and international organizations in various spheres, as well as its geography and scope are becoming more extensive. In particular, "Active relations with the United Nations, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, and the Commonwealth of independent states, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation and other international organizations serve the national interests of Uzbekistan"[1]. The establishment and development of bilateral relations with foreign countries around the world is an integral part of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is more significant because the establishment of bilateral cooperation not only serves the interests of the two countries but also serves to establish a friendship, mutual respect, and friendly relations between the peoples living in these countries. One such country is the Republic of South Korea, which has a great place not only in the Asian region but also in the world community. It is necessary to say that the establishment of relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the Republic of South Korea was beneficial for both sides. The reason is that currently there are several hundred thousand Korean people who live in Uzbekistan. It should be noted that the warm attitude of the two nations to each other demonstrates a positive impact on cooperation between the two countries. Since the earliest days of cooperation up to the present days, relations between the two countries have been developing steadily. We can see this from the point of view expressed by the leaders of the states. The following viewpoints of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev are a clear example of this. "The Republic of South Korea and the Republic of Uzbekistan are strategic partners. South Korea has a reputation in the world as a highly developed, state with a huge economic, scientific-technical, innovative, and intellectual

potential. We highly appreciate our cooperation, which is decided based on openness, mutual understanding, and respect for interests."

The advantage of the cooperation established with the Republic of South Korea over cooperation with other countries was that during the years of independent development the Republic of South Korea became one of the most developed countries in the world, gaining a new economic image with modern scientific research and educational achievements. In recent years, the direction, procedure, rule, and level of cultural, scientific, and technical relations in the sphere of education between South Korea and Uzbekistan have been reflected in the official documents adopted at the official meetings of two leaders. It should be noted that the relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of South Korea are consistently developing based on the Joint Declaration on Strategic Partnership signed in 2006, the Joint Declaration on further development and deepening of the Strategic Partnership adopted in 2014 and other important documents[3]. In particular, the official visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Republic of South Korea on November 22, 2017, the official visit of the President of the Republic of South Korea Moon Jae-in to the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 18-21, 2019 was one of the most important events in the history of Uzbek-South Korean cooperation and brought the relations between the two countries to the level of "Special Strategic Partnership." Effective negotiations and events held in a friendly and practical environment with the participation of the leaders of States confirmed the importance of further continuation of active political dialogue at the highest level. It is a determining factor in maintaining mutual trust and openness between the two countries. The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of South Korea signed a joint declaration on a separate strategic partnership, 16 intergovernmental and interdepartmental documents, as well as a package of agreements worth more than 12 billion dollars in the trade, economic and investment spheres. The Joint Declaration on a strategic partnership between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of South Korea has launched a new stage in the history of Uzbek-South Korean relations aimed at deepening the mutual cooperation between the two countries in the political, trade-economic, investment, financial-technical and cultural-humanitarian spheres. Presidential Decree "On measures to further expand and strengthen cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of South Korea" was adopted to ensure complete and high-quality implementation of bilateral agreements and treaties signed during the state visit of the president of the Republic of South Korea to the Republic of Uzbekistan. Further improvement of relations between the two countries is becoming increasingly important. Many agreements and treaties were signed that were beneficial to both countries during the visits of the leaders of the two countries. The relations between these two countries in the field of education are also developing rapidly and entering a new level in terms of quantity and quality. It should be noted that in the history of relations between the two countries, the educational and cultural sphere has played a significant role. The most important cooperation in the field of education is the ongoing cooperation in higher education. In this regard, it would be appropriate to cite Article 33 entitled "International Cooperation" of the Law "On Education": "Educational institutions participate in international cooperation on educational issues, have the right to establish direct contacts with relevant educational institutions of foreign countries, to establish joint educational institutions with them following the procedure established by the

legislation". Higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan have established cooperation with more than 30 scientific research institutions of the Republic of South Korea. The opening of Inha University in Tashkent in 2014 raised relations to a new level in this regard. This higher educational institution is the first foreign university that makes a worthy contribution to the training of highly qualified IT specialists at the level of international standards. Currently, more than thousands of students study at the university in the field of information technology, engineering, and logistics. It is also planned to open branches of several higher education institutions of the Republic of South Korea in Uzbekistan in the future. This will serve to further strengthen relations between the two countries.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. Ensure the law and the interests of the people are the key to the development of the country and the prosperity of the people. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - P.
2. The newspaper People's Speech April 19, 2019 № 79, p.1
3. Uzbekistan-South Korea: a new stage in strategic partnership // People's speech. November 24, 2017. № 237. p 1.
4. Higher education. A set of regulatory documents. Tashkent: Sharq, 2001. p. 15.

